

CONSUMER'S BEHAVIOR STUDY OF ORGANIC PRODUCTS IN THE POST-PANDEMIC PERIOD

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Abstract

Purpose – *Informing and documenting the psychological profile of the consumer of organic products.*

Methodology/approach – *The research method used is the survey, and the research tool used is the questionnaire applied to each subject.*

Findings – *The Internet is the primary source of information regarding purchases, for both organic and traditional products. Although the term organic can be assimilated with a multitude of specifications, the subjects associate organic products with healthy products. The consumers of these products are satisfied with the characteristics, the benefits brought, but also with their price. Although they are more expensive, the subjects are willing to spend a significant amount every month.*

Research limitations/implications – *The questioned subjects refer to a general context of organic products, the range of food and non-food products being very wide.*

Practical implications – *Applying research tools every 6 months would be effective to see how the consumers situation of organic products has changed, taking into account that lifestyle variables are not constant and they change over time. A longitudinal study would allow observing changes in consumer preferences over time.*

Originality/value – *Green marketing aims not only to sell or win long-term customers, but to create a better world by offering green products. The consumption of these products increases the quality of life and contributes to supporting the environment.*

Key words: *post-pandemic consumer behavior, organic products, ecological marketing*

Introduction

Green marketing aims not only to sell or gain long-term customers, but more than that, to create a better world by offering products that support and improve the environment.

In order to understand and achieve this, it is necessary for organizations to know the ecology of the market, namely the laws and the current production and consumption systems, and then with the help of this knowledge certain policies are established that oversee the efficient use of the resources used, as well as the processes utilized. Organizations should use coherent and solid green marketing strategies that look not only at advertising communication, but also at the production process, from the use of raw materials, to the creation of packaging and disposal of waste.

The demand for organic products has increased, and the pandemic period has accelerated this trend, which is continuously growing even in the post-pandemic period.

In the post-pandemic period, the evolution of the consumer goods market reflects the habits during the pandemic era regarding the consumption of organic products, either food or non-food, which led to increased sales.

In this paper, a marketing research was carried out regarding the use of organic products also in the post-pandemic period, with the aim of providing as much information as possible about consumers, specifically about their opinions, attitude and behavior.

Although consumers are increasingly attentive to the use of materials or ingredients and to the production processes that are more or less sustainable, often they do not have much specific knowledge on this topic, thus the sphere of information becomes an extremely important factor considering the multitude of erroneous information given by some organizations that do not behave properly towards the environment.

Conceptual Aspects Specific to Marketing Research

In order to implement and design the best marketing strategies, knowing the market, the consumer behaviors and their opinions is vital. Marketers pay attention to both the people who buy, use and consume the products or services and also to the factors that can influence the purchase and consumption [Cătoiu, I., Marketing research - treaty, Publisher Uranus, Bucharest, 2009].

In essence, the American Marketing Association defines marketing research as the systematic collection, recording, storage, and examination of data on aspects related to the marketing of goods and services.

The father of marketing, Philip Kotler defines marketing research as "the systematic design, collection, analysis and reporting of data and conclusions regarding a situation that the company faces in the market" [Laura Bacali (coordinator) – Manual of Economic Engineering, Marketing, Publisher "Dacia",2002].

The mission of market research is to strengthen the marketing decision.

Market research seeks and elaborates answers to one or almost all of the essential questions presented in figure 1. intended for a marketing situation.

Figure 1. Essential questions of market research

[Gabriel-Petru Luca, Laura Bacali – Management of Ecologic Marketing, Publisher " Gh. Asachi", Iași, 2003]

The functions of marketing research can be summarized as:

- the descriptive function, which consists in the research and presentation of reality, of the existing state in essence;
- the diagnostic function, which consists in explaining reality;
- the predictive function, which consists in predicting the results, effects following marketing decisions, based on descriptive research and diagnostics;
- the projective function, which involves supporting the development of a long-term strategy, by increasing the company's active mission in relation to environmental changes, based on the optimal allocation of resources, i.e. by supporting the company to follow an anticipatory-active attitude on the market.

Summarizing the above, research is the function of marketing that with the help of information connects the customer, the consumer and the general public to the marketer.

Marketing research covers a multitude of areas, such as: analysis of market characteristics, allowance of potential market and its evolution, sales analysis, market segmentation studies, sales forecasting, price related studies, product image research, evaluation of sales methods, testing marketing programs,

products and packaging, analysis of direct and indirect competitors [Gabriel-Petru Luca, Laura Bacali – Management of Ecologic Marketing, Publisher “ Gh. Asachi”, Iași, 2003]

Objectives of marketing research:

- knowing the environment in which the organization operates;
 - identify the organization’s opportunities on the respective market;
 - determine the action alternatives for the respective organization;
 - choose an optimal version from those alternatives
- [<https://www.studocu.com/ro/document/academia-de-studii-economice-din-bucuresti/cercetari-de-marketing> (accessed on 15.05.2022)].

The multitude of relationships the organizations have with the environment generates a variety of themes for marketing research. Grouping them based on categories of research activities includes the following:

- researches at micro and macro-economic level;
- price research;
- distribution research;
- product research
- research on promotion;
- purchasing behavior research [Laura Bacali (coordinator) – Manual of Economic Engineering, Marketing, Publisher “Dacia”,2002].

The complexity of processes and phenomena targeted by marketing research involves numerous ways of studying them. Thus, numerous research variants were developed which were included in certain criteria that form the typology of marketing research, presented in figure 2. below.

Figure 2. Typology of marketing research [Gabriel-Petru Luca, Laura Bacali – Management of Ecologic Marketing, Publisher “ Gh. Asachi”, Iași, 2003]

Exploratory research has the role of clarifying aspects related to problems faced by decision-makers, while descriptive research has the objective of describing the marketing phenomena that takes place and determining their frequency of occurrence.

Instrumental research is intended for testing and validating some research tools or methods, such as the questionnaire, while causal research has the role of identifying and knowing the relationships between variables. Predictive research aims to make a forecast of marketing phenomena, on different terms (short, medium, long).

Office research has as information reports, statistics, which can be easily obtained and studied in the office, while onsite research involves the travel of the researcher to the source.

Regarding the frequency of conducting research, it can be periodic, when it is carried out at certain time intervals, and occasional, when it is no longer repeated in time [<https://www.studocu.com/ro/document/academia-de-studii-economice-din-bucuresti/cercetari-de-marketing-cercetari-de-marketing/continutul-si-sfera-cercetarii-de-marketing/2310040> (accessed on 16.05.2022)].

Marketing Research Process

Based on a multilateral analysis, a marketing research can be established through the process of grounding and adopting some decisions. For the successful conduct of a marketing research, the following steps are taken:

- Preliminary investigation;
- Elaboration of the research program;
- Collection of data and information;
- Information analysis;
- Writing and presenting the research report [Laura Bacali (coordinator) – Manual of Economic Engineering, Marketing, Publisher “Dacia”,2002].

Preliminary Investigation

The preliminary investigation is the initial phase of the investigation. This stage aims to identify the problem, define the purpose of the research, develop working hypotheses and anticipate the value of the information obtained through the research.

Identifying the problem and defining the purpose of the research are important stages in the research process and have a determining influence on the other phases or stages.

In the present paper, a marketing research was carried out in order to know people's perception for both food and non-food organic products.

Formulating the objectives and hypotheses is an equally important stage, with a direct impact on the research methodology and its costs.

By formulating the objectives it is possible to specify what information is needed regarding the grounding of decisional alternatives for any problem investigated.

The main objective of the research is to identify the opinions of the subjects towards organic products. As secondary objectives, we aim to obtain: information on the frequency of purchasing organic products, the type of organic products purchased, the level of satisfaction following the purchase and also the evaluation of their price.

The assumptions underlying the research and the elaborated questionnaire are:

1. The majority of respondents use the Internet as their main source of information when shopping in general.
2. All respondents know the term of organic product.

3. A large part of respondents believe that the advantage of organic products is that they are healthier than the classical ones.
4. More than half of the respondents associate organic products to healthy products.
5. The majority of respondents consider organic products to be trustworthy due to the advantages they offer.
6. Most respondents have purchased organic products at least once.
7. Respondents decide which organic products to buy by getting information from friends and family.
8. Half of the respondents have a high degree of satisfaction with organic products.
9. A large part of the respondents consider that the price of organic products corresponds to their value.
10. More than half of the respondents allocate, on average, a maximum of 10% of their income for the consumption of organic products monthly.
11. Most of the respondents have bought organic food products up to now.
12. A large part of the respondents believe that in the future they will purchase organic products.

Research Program Development

In developing the research program, the survey method was used, we developed a questionnaire that was then distributed on online platforms and was applied to each subject.

The questionnaire was built according to the funnel principle, from general questions to specific ones. It contained both closed-ended, dichotomous, multichotomous, scaled responses and open-ended, completely unstructured questions and was pretested on a sample of 10 subjects, who were not subsequently included in the final sample. Following the pretest, the necessary changes were made to the questions, as well as the answers, and then the questionnaire was drafted in its final form.

A non-random research method, based on accessibility, was used for the selection of subjects.

The final sampling includes 70 subjects, natural persons, of which 44.3% are male and 55.7% are female, belonging to both urban and rural environments, some with secondary education and others with higher education.

Data and Information Analysis

At this stage, the results obtained from the research are presented descriptively and also in graphic form.

At the first question of the completed questionnaire, the respondents specified the sources of information in relation to the products they purchase, the results being concretized according to the following graph:

Figure 3. Sources of information related to purchased products

According to the results presented in Figure 3, the majority of the respondents, representing 91.4% of the percentage of 100%, purchase products using the Internet as a source of information. This option is chosen by 64 people out of 70. In a percentage of 32.9% respondents get information through close people, 17.1% through television, and 2.9% through radio. In addition to the answer options presented in the questionnaire, one respondent states that he relies on his own information when purchasing products in general.

Thus, the hypothesis corresponding to this question "Most respondents have the Internet as their main source of information" is confirmed at the level of the investigated sample.

Figure 4. Number of subjects who have or have not heard of organic products

With the second question of the questionnaire, we wanted to identify the subjects who are aware of organic products.

According to the results presented in figure 4, most of the respondents are familiar with organic products, besides 1.4% who represents a subject who has not heard of organic products. Following the results obtained, it can be stated that the hypothesis that was the basis of this question "All respondents know the term organic product." is denied, because one of the respondents does not know the term of organic product.

Question number three, an open question, through which the subjects mentioned the advantages of organic products, compared to classic ones.

Figure 5. The advantages of organic products compared to classic ones

By summarizing the responses recorded to this question, the main statements of the subjects are identified. In this situation, the answers were inserted into the Excel application, where they were centralized, and the below graph was generated.

The results indicate a percentage of 29% where the subjects declared that the advantage of organic products compared to classic ones is that they are healthier. 13% of subjects believe that organic products reduce pollution, 11% believe that they have a higher quality, 8% that they protect the environment, 6% believe that they are better, and 5% believe that organic products are more natural. With a percentages of 2%, the subjects believe that organic products help the ecosystem and are not harmful to the planet, have nutritional values, do not contain pesticides, herbicides, hormones, genetically modified organisms and additives, have a lower carbon footprint than classic ones and have a composition without additives and preservatives. There was also a percentage of 3% which considered that organic products have no advantage over conventional products.

The hypothesis behind this question "A large part of the respondents believe that the advantage of organic products compared to conventional ones is that they are healthier." it is confirmed at the level of the investigated sample.

Next, we wanted to know the respondents' perception of the organic product.

Figure 6. Organic product's significance

According to the results obtained, following the analysis, it can be observed that the highest value was obtained by the characteristic "Healthy product", with a percentage of 70%, meaning 49 of the total respondents. Also, a large part of the respondents, 50%, representing a number of 35 subjects, consider that the organic product is equivalent to the natural product, 47.1% to the recyclable product, 32.9% to a product without preservatives, and in a lower percentage, of 8.6% to the vegetable product.

The hypothesis "More than half of the respondents believe that organic products are equivalent to healthy products" is confirmed.

In the following, we wanted to identify the credibility of the organic products's advantages for the subjects.

Figure 7. Credibility of the organic products's advantages for the subjects.

According to the above graph, a percentage of 40.7%, meaning 24 of respondents, consider the advantages of organic products to be credible, and 17.1% consider their advantages to be very credible. The other variants are found in smaller proportions: 4.3%, in the number of three subjects, those who consider them less credible, 2.9% those who do not know this aspect and 1.4%, a percentage represented by a single subject, those who consider the advantages of organic products to be at all credible. Hypothesis "Most respondents consider organic products to be credible." it is confirmed at the level of the investigated sample.

The following question analyzes the percentage of subjects who have ever purchased organic products.

Figure 8. Subjects affirmation in regards to purchasing organic products

The majority, 91.4%, meaning 64 subjects claim to have purchased organic products. On the other hand, 8.6%, meaning 6 subjects state that they have never purchased organic products. Following the results obtained, the hypothesis "Most respondents have purchased organic products at least once" is confirmed.

Further on, we will investigate the sources of information used by the subjects when deciding which organic products to purchase.

Figure 9. Sources of information used when purchasing organic products

Summarizing the responses recorded to this question, it appears that the majority of respondents, representing 76.2% of the total percentage of 100%, purchase products using the Internet as a source of information. 52.4% of the respondents get information through family, and 39.7% through friends. In addition to the answer options presented in the questionnaire, one respondent states that he relies on his own knowledge when purchasing organic products.

Thus, the hypothesis corresponding to this question "Respondents decide which organic products to buy by getting information from friends and family" is disproved at the level of the investigated sample, because the Internet is the predominant source of information chosen by the subjects.

The purpose of the eight question is to identify the degree of satisfaction of the respondents towards the organic products bought.

8. On a scale from 1 to 5, in which 1 is the lowest and 5 is the highest, what is the satisfaction level towards the purchased organic products?

Figure 10. The satisfaction level provided by the purchased organic products

We analyzed the purchasing situation of both food and non-food products.

Regarding the food products, most of the respondents have a high degree of satisfaction with the organic products bought, 20 respondents choosing criterion 4 from the graph. A number of 18 respondents have an average degree of satisfaction, opting for criterion number 3 in the graph, and at a small difference, with a number of 15 respondents, there is criterion number 5 which represents a very high degree of satisfaction with the food based organic products bought. On the other hand, in the graph analyzed, there are also respondents who are less satisfied with the purchased organic products, 10 and respectively one respondent with low and very low degree of satisfaction, represented by criterion 1 and 2 in the graph.

Regarding non-food products, the situation is opposite to food products. The maximum degree of satisfaction being the lowest percentage in the graph, selected by 8 subjects. It is noted that 21 subjects have a high degree of satisfaction with the non-food products purchased, 19 subjects have an average degree of satisfaction, and 12 subjects have a low degree of satisfaction.

The hypothesis that was the basis of this question "Half of the respondents have a high degree of satisfaction with organic products." is confirmed.

Through the following question, respondents had the opportunity to express their opinion with regards to the price of organic products compared to classic ones.

9. What do you think of the price of organic products compared to classic ones?
64 answers

Figure 11. Subjects' view in regards to the price of organic products compared to classic ones

Following the graph's analysis, it is noted that more than half of the respondents believe that the price of organic products compared to the classic ones corresponds to their value, as a majority, with a percentage of 51.6%. A number of 24 respondents believe that the price of organic products is too high compared to that of classic products, and 7 respondents think that organic products have an acceptable price.

Hypothesis "A large part of the respondents believe that the price of organic products corresponds to their value." is confirmed.

The next question has a close connection with the previous one, thereby wanting to find out the subjects' opinion regarding the price given to organic products in accordance with their value.

10. Do you believe the price of organic products matches their value?
64 answers

Figure 12. Subjects' opinion on the price and value of organic products

According to the above graph, a share of 59.4%, meaning 38 respondents out of 70, consider that the price of organic products is partially appropriate to their value, 32.8% consider that the price of organic products is entirely appropriate to their value, and 7.8% believe that the price of organic products does not correspond to their value.

The hypothesis that was the basis of this question was confirmed at the level of the investigated sample: "A large part of the respondents believe that the price of organic products corresponds to their value".

Next, we wanted to identify the percentage of income that the respondents are willing to allocate monthly for the consumption of organic products.

11. How much money are you willing to spend on average, monthly, for purchasing organic products?
64 answers

Figure 13. The monthly percentage allocated for the consumption of organic products

The results shown in figure 13. reveal a share of 40.6% of the investigated subjects who allocate an average of 10% of their income monthly for the consumption of organic products, this being the predominant percentage in the graph. With a percentages of 28.1% subjects are willing to allocate between 10 and 20% of their income, 7.8%, meaning a number of 8 respondents are willing to spend more than 20% of their income, and 15 of them (23, 4%) do not know the percentage they are willing to allocate on average monthly for the consumption of organic products.

The hypothesis behind this question "More than half of the respondents allocate on average a maximum of 10% of their income per month for the consumption of organic products." is refuted, because only 40.6% of the respondents allocate 10% of the income, while the rest spend above the average formulated in the hypothesis.

Considering the diversity with which organic products have evolved in general, the following question wanted to know the types of products purchased most often.

12. What type of organic products you purchased?
64 answers

Figure 14. Type of organic products purchased

Following the analysis of the above graph, it is found that food based products are predominantly bought by the respondents, the graph showing a percentage of 95.3%, meaning a number of 61 subjects in the case of this variant, and in the case of non-food products, a percentage of 32.8%, meaning a number of 21 subjects.

The hypothesis behind this question "The majority of respondents have bought organic food products so far." is confirmed.

Question number 13 is identified as a complicated question, a control question, concerning the attitude, motivation and opinion of subjects. Within this, it is desired to identify the subjects' intentions towards the purchase of organic products in the future.

13. Do you believe you will purchase organic products in the future?
70 answers

Figure 15. Subjects' intentions towards the purchase of organic products in the future

According to the graph, most respondents want to purchase organic products in the future, 42.9% answering "Definitely yes", and 45.7% answering "Probably yes". In smaller proportions, 4.3% probably wouldn't buy and 1.4% definitely wouldn't buy, and 5.7% of them don't know.

Thus, the hypothesis corresponding to this question "A large part of the respondents believe that in the future they will be purchasing organic products" is confirmed at the level of the investigated sample.

According to the principle to which the questionnaire was built, the "funnel principle", after the general questions follow the specific or identification questions, which served for analyzing the responses in the questionnaire, under the protection of anonymity.

The first identifying question is related to the age of the subjects. Thus, according to the results, of the total of 70 respondents, 77.1% are between 18-35 years old, 14.3% are over 45 years old, and then, equally, with a percentage of 4, 3% are respondents aged between 35-45 and those under 18.

14. age
70 answers

Figure 16. Subjects' distribution according to age

Next question corresponds to the level of education of the respondents.

According to the results illustrated in the below graph, the majority of the subjects (57.1%), meaning 40 people out of the total of 70, have university degrees. A share of 22.9% consisting of 16 subjects have high school education, 10%, registering 7 respondents, have university education, 5.7% have secondary school education, and finally, with equal percentages of 1.4% have post-high school education and professional.

15. Educational degree
70 answers

Figure 17. Subjects' distribution according to educational level

Through this question, the demographic data of the subjects needed for the statistical analysis of the data was analyzed. It is noted that more than half live in urban areas (55.7%) and 31 of them (44.3%) in rural areas.

16. Living area
70 answers

Figure 18. Subjects' distribution according to living area

Question number 17 was ment to investigate the gender of the persons involved in the survey. Thus, the results show that the female part is predominant with a percentage of 55.7%, meaning 39 people out of the total of 70, and the male part represents 44.3%, meaning 31 respondents.

17. Gender
70 answers

Figure 19. Subjects' distribution according to gender

Finally, the surveyors wanted to identify the average monthly net income per family member of the investigated subjects. The results illustrated in figure 20 show that 28 people out of a total of 70, representing 40%, have an income between 2000 and 4000 lei. In a share of 27.1%, 19 people have an income between 1000-2000 lei, 21.4% below 1000 lei, and the remaining 11.4% of the total respondents, meaning 8 people, benefit from an average income over 4000 lei monthly.

18. The average monthly net income per family member
70 answers

Figure 20. Subjects' distribution according to the average monthly net income per family member

Conclusions

A company's image plays an important role in its development, thus in order to increase its degree of appreciation among the public, but also of the market on which it operates, companies turn to organic marketing.

Green marketing, an integral part of social marketing that seeks to satisfy consumers' needs to a greater degree than competitors, while enhancing their well-being and the environment in which they live, proposes a set of product, prices, promotions, and distribution policies that can ensure and maintain a cleaner environment and healthier consumption to maximize the quality of life.

An important role in buying organic products is to inform consumers about healthy food, care for the environment, awareness of using resources rationally and living in harmony with the environment.

The study resulted in information regarding the psychological profile of the organic products consumer, discovering a complex outline. The information refers to his opinion on organic products, on the selling price, the frequency of purchasing, the type of organic products consumed as well as on socio-demographics factors.

Based on the answers obtained, the following conclusions were drawn:

The Internet is the main source through which the respondents inform themselves about purchases, whether they are organic or traditional products.

Although the organic term can be assimilated with a multitude of specifications, the surveyed people believe that organic products are associated with healthy products.

From the analysis of the questionnaire, it is acquired that the subjects who are used to purchasing organic products are quite satisfied with their characteristics and the benefits they bring.

A good part of the respondents are satisfied with the price organic products have, considering that it corresponds to the offered value.

Although sometimes organic products can be quite expensive, the respondents are willing to spend a significant part of their monthly salary on purchasing them.

By associating the satisfaction organic products' advantages offer, as well as their price, the subjects believe that they will keep purchasing the products in the future, as well.

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